

EXPERIENCE IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ASCENDING AORTIC ANEURYSMS

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Background

The diagnosis and surgical management of ascending aortic aneurysms remain among the most challenging aspects of modern cardiovascular surgery. In 66.6% of cases, a standard one-stage Bentall procedure was performed. Our experience also includes cases of ascending aortic aneurysm associated with coarctation, and we aim to present our surgical approach and outcomes.

Methods

Between January 1, 2010, and January 1, 2022, 41 patients with ascending aortic aneurysms underwent the Bentall procedure at the Republican Specialized Center of Surgery. The study cohort included 26 males (63%) and 15 females (37%), with ages ranging from 25 to 65 years (mean age: 31.6 ± 0.2 years).

The etiological factors included **Marfan syndrome** in 24 patients (58.5%), **atherosclerosis** in 14 patients (34.1%), and **degenerative aortic disease** in 3 patients (7.3%). Aortic dissection (DeBakey Type II) was observed in 12 patients (29.2%), while 18 patients (43.9%) underwent surgery without signs of dissection. Additionally, **bicuspid aortic valve** was identified in 8 cases (19.5%).

Three patients (7.3%) had an **ascending aortic aneurysm associated with coarctation of the aorta** at a typical location. In these cases, a **two-stage surgical approach** was employed: the first stage involved **resection of the coarctation with conduit replacement**, followed by the **Bentall procedure 10–12 days later**, yielding excellent outcomes.

Results

The **hospital mortality rate** was 9.7% (4 patients), with causes of death including acute heart failure, refractory postoperative bleeding, and multiple organ failure.

Conclusions

Despite certain complications and technical challenges, the **Bentall procedure** ensures adequate radical correction of ascending aortic aneurysms. It demonstrates excellent **short- and long-term survival rates** and a low incidence of reoperation. Therefore, this approach can be recommended across a broad range of etiologies, including complex aortic pathologies such as coarctation.